

A SUCCESS MODEL FOR COFFEE SHOP ENTREPRENEURS IN THAILAND

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Abstract

This research aims to: 1) assess the levels of entrepreneurial leadership, business acumen, 8Ps marketing strategy implementation, management innovation, and success among coffee shop entrepreneurs in Thailand; 2) examine the impact of entrepreneurial leadership, business acumen, 8Ps marketing strategies, and management innovation on the success of coffee shop entrepreneurs in Thailand; and 3) devise a success model for coffee shop entrepreneurs in Thailand. The research employs a mixed-methods approach, with quantitative research involving 400 coffee shop entrepreneurs in Thailand. Sampling was conducted proportionally, with questionnaires used for data collection and analysis done using structural equation modeling. Qualitative research entailed in-depth interviews with ten coffee shop entrepreneurs and ten industry experts. Findings indicate high levels of entrepreneurial attributes and their significant influence on success. The IOCSS Model (Insider and Outsider Strategy for Success of Coffee Shop Entrepreneurs in Thailand) was developed as a result, emphasizing product differentiation, adherence to international service standards, partnership building, and leveraging digital marketing technology for enhanced customer engagement. These findings can serve as a blueprint for policymakers aiming to foster sustainable success among coffee shop entrepreneurs in Thailand.

Keywords: Coffee Shop, Business, Entrepreneur, Thailand.

INTRODUCTION

Driving the country's development amidst ever-evolving trends requires a focus on internal resilience, enabling steady growth amidst external fluctuations while considering economic, social, and environmental sustainability [1]. By fostering the principles of Sufficiency Economy, Thailand aims to achieve stability, prosperity, and sustainability. Emphasis must be placed on striking a balance in various dimensions, including competitiveness with foreign nations and self-reliance, as well as equitable distribution of opportunities to reduce inequality among different groups and regions [2].

Moreover, maintaining ecological balance is essential for sustainable coexistence with natural resources and the environment [3],[4],[5]. Effective management of national institutions is crucial for addressing both external and internal challenges.

Developing resilience to swiftly adapt to changes is vital, encompassing readiness for survival, sufficiency, and transitioning towards sustainable growth. Enhancing the competitiveness of domestic manufacturers plays a pivotal role in achieving quality-driven and sustainable development [6],[7].

Promoting and fostering entrepreneurship [8], particularly in utilizing innovation and technology for goods and services production, is pivotal for enhancing business efficiency and meeting diverse customer [9],[10] needs across all target segments. The coffee shop industry is one such sector promoted under this policy, aimed at collectively driving steady economic growth in the country. The beverage industry's revenue is anticipated to parallel the growth of the domestic market from 2022 to 2024. In 2020, Thailand's beverage market boasted a consumption volume of 13 billion liters, valued at approximately 720 billion baht, with non-alcoholic beverages dominating consumption (79%) and alcoholic beverages dominating in terms of value (64%). Currently, the coffee production industry in Thailand is experiencing growth, particularly in the northern region.

This expansion is reflected in the increasing income generated by coffee businesses [11] and the rising popularity of coffee beverages, leading to high market demand. This growth trend presents numerous opportunities for entrepreneurs to enhance their market share. Improving coffee quality to meet industry standards can add value and facilitate market expansion, attracting new entrants into the coffee shop business sector. Innovations aimed at improving product efficiency and enhancing service processes can further strengthen market competitiveness [12].

As of 2023, there are 796 registered coffee shops in Thailand, with the majority located in the northern region (29.85%), followed by Bangkok (29.07%), and the provinces of Chiang Mai and Chiang Rai. The northern region is particularly prominent for coffee production, primarily cultivating the Arabica variety. In contrast, the southern region focuses on Robusta cultivation, supported by government initiatives as coffee serves as an economic crop. Businesses aiming [13] to sustainably increase their market share often employ a blend of marketing strategies to cater to customer needs. Utilizing sales personnel plays a crucial role in achieving business success, while promotions can effectively boost sales. Enhancing the quality of coffee products instills confidence in customers, influencing their purchasing decisions positively. Effective marketing communication is essential for shaping customer perceptions, with entrepreneurs frequently employing strategies to raise awareness among their target audience [14].

Introducing new ideas and methodologies can enhance business efficiency [15] and confer a competitive edge, particularly through the strategic use of technology. Successful entrepreneurs integrate innovation into their business processes, with service innovation offering opportunities to foster customer satisfaction and loyalty. Embracing innovation enables organizations to respond adeptly to customer needs, positioning them effectively in the market. The coffee shop industry [10],[13] has faced challenges recently due to the spread of viral infections, leading to closures of many establishments. However, as conditions have improved, numerous new entrepreneurs have entered the market, resulting in heightened competition. Entrepreneurs who fail to establish market dominance may struggle to sustain their businesses, leading to decreased market share and potential liquidation. Consequently, running coffee shops efficiently has become a pressing concern for entrepreneurs. Therefore, the researcher aims to investigate a success model for coffee shop operators in Thailand. This study seeks to empower coffee shop operators to compete sustainably in the market.

Research Objectives

- 1) To study the level of leadership variables of entrepreneurs. Ability to conduct business 8Ps Marketing Strategy, Management Innovation and Success of Coffee Shop Entrepreneurs in Thailand
- 2) To study the influence of entrepreneurial leadership variables. Ability to conduct business 8Ps marketing strategies and management innovations that affect the success of coffee shop operators in Thailand
- 3) To create a model for the success of coffee shop operators in Thailand.

Scope of Research

Demographic scope and sample group.

In this study, the population consists of 796 coffee shop operators in Thailand, as reported by the Department of Business Development, Ministry of Commerce in 2023. For the quantitative sample, the sample size was determined based on proportions. According to the criterion of having at least 20 times the number of observed variables, and since this research involves 20 observed variables, the researcher decided on a sample size of 400. As for the qualitative aspect, the researcher conducted in-depth interviews with 10 coffee shop entrepreneurs and 10 coffee shop business experts in Thailand, totaling 20 participants. Purposive sampling was employed to select specific informants, and content analysis was used to analyze the data.

Variable.

Variables used in this research the researcher reviewed the literature and was able to summarize the variables in this study into 2 categories: 1. Internal Variable is the management innovation and success of coffee shop operators in Thailand. 2. External Variable is the leadership of the entrepreneur. Ability in business operations and marketing strategy 8Ps

RESEARCH RESULTS

The findings reveal that the majority of the sample were female, comprising 206 individuals, which accounts for 51.50 percent of the total sample size. Additionally, individuals aged between 36 to 45 years constituted a significant portion, with 156 people, representing 39.00 percent of the sample. Moreover, those holding a Bachelor's degree level were predominant, totaling 212 individuals, making up 53.00 percent of the sample. Lastly, individuals with a monthly business income of less than 1,000,000 baht were prevalent, with 248 people, accounting for 62.00 percent of the sample.

Results of the study of entrepreneurial leadership variables. Ability to conduct business, marketing strategy, 8 Ps, management innovation and success Coffee shop operators in Thailand

The mean and standard deviation for the level of leadership variables of entrepreneurs, ability to conduct business, and 8Ps marketing strategy, innovation, management, and success of coffee shop operators in Thailand (n=400) are as follows: Leadership of Entrepreneurs

(ETPLDS): Mean: 4.36 Interpretation: The leadership of entrepreneurs is at a high level. Individual Aspects: Decision Making (DECMK), Knowledge and Ability (KNAB), Marketing (MRKT): Average between 4.26 - 4.47. Ability to Conduct Business (ABLBUS): Mean: 4.32 Interpretation: The ability to conduct business is at a high level. Individual Aspects: Policy Aspect (PLIC), Management Aspect (MNGT), Operational Aspect (OPRT): Average between 4.07 - 4.49. The mean and standard deviation for the marketing strategy variable (EGSTG) among coffee shop operators in Thailand (n=400) are as follows: Mean: 4.16 Interpretation: The marketing strategy is at a high level. When considering each aspect, the following individual aspects were found: Product Strategy (PODT) Mean: Average between 3.76 - 4.44 Interpretation: Product strategy is at a high level. Price Strategy (PRIC) Mean: Average between 3.76 - 4.44 Interpretation: Price strategy is at a high level. Distribution Strategy (DIST) Mean: Average between 3.76 - 4.44. Interpretation: Distribution strategy is at a high level. Marketing Promotion Strategy (PROM) Mean: Average between 3.76 - 4.44 Interpretation: Marketing promotion strategy is at a high level. Packaging Strategy (PACK) Mean: Average between 3.76 - 4.44 Interpretation: Packaging strategy is at a high level. Salesperson Strategy (SLSTF) Mean: Average between 3.76 - 4.44 Interpretation: Salesperson strategy is at a high level. News Strategy (NEWS) Mean: Average between 3.76 - 4.44 Interpretation: News strategy is at a high level. Tactics for Using Power (POWE) Mean: Average between 3.76 - 4.44 Interpretation: Tactics for using power are at a high level.

The mean and standard deviation for the management innovation variable (INMNG) among coffee shop operators in Thailand (n=400) are as follows: Mean: 4.34 Interpretation: Management innovation is at a high level. When considering each aspect, the following individual aspects were found: Use of Technology in Business (TECH) Mean: Average between 4.21 - 4.42 Interpretation: The use of technology in business is at a high level. Process Innovation (PRCS) Mean: Average between 4.21 - 4.42 Interpretation: Process innovation is at a high level. Service Innovation (SERV) Mean: Average between 4.21 - 4.42 Interpretation: Service innovation is at a high level. The mean and standard deviation for the success of coffee shop operators in Thailand (SCSOT) variable among the sample of 400 operators are as follows: Mean: 4.43 Interpretation: The success of coffee shop operators in Thailand is at a high level. When considering each aspect, the following individual aspects were found: Continuously Increased Operating Results (ICPRO) Mean: 4.54 Interpretation: Continuously increased operating results are at the highest level. Gaining Loyalty from Customers (LOYCS) Mean: Average between 4.28 - 4.47 Interpretation: Gaining loyalty from customers is at a high level. Having Market Power (MRKPW) Mean: Average between 4.28 - 4.47 Interpretation: Having market power is at a high level. The results of the study, which analyzed the influence of entrepreneurial leadership variables, ability to conduct business, 8 Ps marketing strategies, and management innovations on the success of coffee shop operators in Thailand, were conducted using the structural equation model analysis technique with the LISREL Version 8.72 program. The analysis proceeded as follows:

1. Normal distribution of empirical variables (n=400): The empirical variables were checked for normal distribution among the sample of 400 coffee shop operators.

2. Correlation coefficient between pairs of empirical variables used in the study in the model (Observation Correlation Test) (n=400): The correlation coefficients between pairs of empirical variables used in the study were examined to assess their relationships within the model.
3. Overall relationships among the empirical variables studied in the structural equation model (n=400): The overall relationships among the empirical variables within the structural equation model were analyzed to understand their collective impact on the success of coffee shop operators.
4. Checking the quality of the measurement model (Measurement Model) studied in the model (n=400): The quality of the measurement model, which included variables related to entrepreneurial leadership, business conduct, marketing strategies, and management innovations, was assessed to ensure its reliability and validity.
5. Results of analysis of the structural equation model based on the hypothesis (Hypothesis Model) (n=400): The structural equation model was analyzed based on the hypotheses formulated to determine the extent of the influence of each variable on the success of coffee shop operators.
6. Results of the analysis of the adjusted structural equation model (Adjust Model) (n=400): The structural equation model was adjusted based on the analysis results to refine the relationships between variables and improve the model's fit to the data.
7. Equations of the structural equation model that is adjusted (Adjust Model) (n=400): The equations of the adjusted structural equation model were derived, specifying the relationships between the variables and their respective coefficients.

These steps provided detailed insights into how entrepreneurial leadership, business conduct, marketing strategies, and management innovations collectively contribute to the success of coffee shop operators in Thailand.

Table 1: Confirm Factor Analysis (Confirm Factor Analysis) Latent variable 8 Ps Marketing Strategy (EGSTG) (n= 400)

Variable	Factor Loading (λ)	Error (θ)	t	R ²
8 Ps Marketing Strategy (EGSTG)				
Product strategy (PODT)	.46	.48	9.36	.52
Pricing Strategy (PRIC)	.70	.51	15.25	.49
Distribution Strategy (DIST)	.61	.63	12.53	.37
Marketing promotion strategy (PROM)	.74	.45	15.27	.55
Packaging strategy (PACK)	.76	.42	16.63	.58
Strategies for using sales staff (SLSTF)	.74	.45	16.38	.55
News strategy (NEWS)	.75	.43	16.21	.57
Strategy for using power (POWE)	.76	.42	16.81	.58
$\rho_c = .89$ $\rho_v = .51$				
Chi-Square=19.93, df=11, P-value=0.04624, RMSEA=0.045				

The presents the analysis of 8 Latent Variables. The 8 Ps Marketing Strategy (EGSTG) comprises 8 components, each with a standardized solution (λ) ranging from .46 to .76,

statistically significant at the .05 level, and a standard error (θ) ranging from .42 to .63. These components collectively explain the variance of the Marketing Strategy 8 Ps (EGSTG) variable. Each indicator variable demonstrates reliability based on the R2 value, ranging from 37% to 58%. The latent variable exhibits component reliability (Composite Reliability, ρ_c) of .89, indicating high reliability. The variance extracted (Average Variable Extracted, ρ_v) has a value of .51.

Chi-Square=19.93, df=11, P-value=0.04624, RMSEA=0.045

Figure 1: Results of confirmatory factor analysis of latent variables. 8 Ps Marketing Strategy (EGSTG) (n=400)

The analysis of the structural equation model based on the hypothesis.

Conduct a check on the harmony of the Hypothesis Model with the empirical data. With the LISREL package, considering the harmony index value, it was found that the hypothetical model was not yet in harmony with the empirical data. Which is considered from the Harmony Index (Fit Index) as follows: $\chi^2 = 905.15$, $df = 161$, $p - \text{value} = .00000$, $\chi^2 / df = 5.62$, $RMSEA = .108$, $RMR = .045$, $SRMR = .058$, $CFI = .97$, $GFI = .82$, $AGFI = .76$, $CN = 112.29$

After careful consideration, the following results were obtained: $\chi^2 = 905.15$, $df. = 161$, $p\text{-value} = .00000$: The criterion is not met as it remains statistically significant. $\chi^2 / df. = 5.62$: The criterion is not met as it still exceeds 2.00. $RMSEA = .108$: The criterion is not met as it still exceeds .05. $RMR = .045$: The criterion is met as the value is less than .05. $SRMR = .058$: The criterion is not yet met as the value exceeds.05. $CFI = .97$: The criterion is met as the value exceeds .90. $GFI = .82$: The criterion is not yet met as the value is less than .90. $AGFI = .76$: The criterion is not yet met as the value is less than .90. $CN = 112.29$: The criterion is not yet met as the value is less than 200.00.

Such results shows that The Hypothesis Model is not as harmonious with the empirical data as it should be. Because the harmony index values, namely χ^2 , χ^2 / df , RMSEA, SRMR, GFI, AGFI and CN, have not yet passed the criteria as specified (Joreskog ; & Sorbom .1996: 121-122), the researcher is still not confident in Estimate various parameters (Parameter Estimation) that occur in the model based on assumptions (Hypothesis Model).

The researcher therefore needs to modify the model (Modification Model) to be consistent with the empirical data. By allowing the variances of the standard errors of some pairs of empirical variables to be related. Considering the suitability and feasibility of concepts and theories. As well as related research results and the possibility of discussing the findings from the model modifications. Until the adjusted model (Adjust Model) is in harmony with the empirical data. Then the relationship path of the model will be considered in detail as follows. The results of the hypothetical model analysis are shown as follows.

Figure 2: Model based on research hypotheses (n= 400)

The analysis of the adjusted structural equation model.

The researcher made adjustments to the hypothetical model to make it harmonious with the empirical data. By allowing the variance of the standard error of χ^2 6 pairs of empirical variables to be related to each other (df before adjustment equal to 16 1 and, df after adjusting, it was equal to 135) until it was found that the adjusted model (Adjust Model) is in harmony with the empirical data. which is considered from the Harmony Index (Fit Index) as follows: $\chi^2 = 258.17$, $df = 135$, $p - value = .00000$, $\chi^2 / df = 1.91$, $RMSEA = .048$, $RMR = .027$, $SRMR = .037$, $CFI = .99$, $GFI = .94$, $AGFI = .91$, $CN = 274.68$

$\chi^2 = 258.17$, $df = 135$, $p\text{-value} = .00000$: The criterion is not met because it remains statistically significant ($p\text{-value} < .05$), as suggested by Harerimana and Mtshali [16]. This is because Test 2 statistic is sensitive to sample size. However, considering the value of χ^2 / df , which is found to be equal to 1.91, it is considered to meet the specified criteria as it is less than 2.00 [17]. RMSEA = .048: It meets the specified criteria as it is less than .05 [18]. RMR = .027: It meets the criteria as the value is less than .05 [19].

SRMR = .037: It meets the criteria as the value is less than .05 [20]. CFI = .99: It meets the criteria as the value is greater than .90 [21]. GFI = .94: It meets the criteria as it is greater than .90 [22]. AGFI = .91: It meets the criteria as it is greater than .90 [22]. CN = 274.68: It meets the criteria as it is greater than 200.00 [22]. Based on these harmony index values, it can be concluded that the adjusted structural equation model (Adjust Model) is in harmony with the empirical data, and the estimation of parameters in such models is therefore acceptable.

Harmony index of the structural equation model that has been adjusted. Harmonious with empirical data which is considered from the Harmony Index (Fit Index) as follows: $\chi^2 = 258.17$, $df = 135$, $p\text{-value} = .00000$, $\chi^2 / df = 1.91$, RMSEA = .048, RMR = .027, SRMR = .037, CFI = .99, GFI = .94, AGFI = .91, CN = 274.68 from the said harmony index values. Therefore, it can be concluded that the structural equation model that is adjusted (Adjust Model) is in harmony with the empirical data and the estimation of parameters in such models is therefore acceptable.

Table 2: The results of estimating the parameters of the coefficients for direct influence (Direct Effect), indirect influence (Indirect Effect), and overall influence (Total Effect) from the modified equation model (n=400) are as follows:

Dependent variable	R ²	Influence	Initial variable			
			INMNG	ETPLDS	ABLBUS	EGSTG
Innovation Management (INMNG)	.87	DE	-	.76* (5.46)	.77* (6.78)	.94* (6.76)
		IE	-	-	-	-
		TE	-	.76* (5.46)	.77* (6.78)	.94* (6.76)
The success of coffee shop operators in Thailand (SCSOT)	.89	DE	.67* (3.96)	.42* (2.71)	-	.49* (6.21)
		IE	-	.44* (3.47)	.65* (4.78)	.43* (3.26)
		TE	.67* (3.965)	.86* (5.74)	.65* (4.78)	.92* (6.52)
$\chi^2 = 258.17$, $df = 135$, $p\text{-value} = .00000$, $\chi^2 / df = 1.91$, RMSEA = .048, RMR = .027, SRMR = .037, CFI = .99, GFI = .94, AGFI = .91, CN = 274.68 * Statistically significant at the .05 level. t-test statistic. If the value is not between - 1.96 and 1.96, it means that it is statistically significant at the .05 level.						

It was found that the structural equation models the influence of entrepreneurial leadership variables Ability to conduct business 8Ps marketing strategies and management innovations that affect the success of coffee shop operators in Thailand the adjustment process (Adjust Model) is in harmony with the empirical data at an acceptable level. Which is considered from the Harmony Index (Fit Index) as follows: $\chi^2 = 258.17$, $df = 135$, $p\text{-value} = .00000$, $\chi^2 / df = 1.91$, RMSEA = .048, RMR = .027, SRMR = .037, CFI = .99, GFI = .94, AGFI = .91, CN = 274.68.

The estimation was found in the structural equation model as follows.

1. Entrepreneurial leadership (ETPLDS) has a direct influence on the success of coffee shop operators in Thailand (SCSOT) with an influence coefficient of $.42^*(2.71)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level is in accordance with research hypothesis number 1, which is stated that Entrepreneurial leadership has a direct influence on the success of coffee shop operators in Thailand.
2. Entrepreneurial leadership (ETPLDS) has a direct influence on Innovation Management (INMNG) with an influence coefficient equal to $.76^*(5.46)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level is in accordance with research hypothesis number 2 which states that Entrepreneurial leadership has a direct influence on management innovation.
3. The ability to conduct business (ABLBUS) has a direct influence on Innovation Management (INMNG) with an influence coefficient equal to $.77^*(6.78)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level is in accordance with research hypothesis number 3 which states that Business ability has a direct influence on management innovation.
4. The 8 Ps marketing strategy (EGSTG) has a direct influence on Innovation Management (INMNG) with an influence coefficient equal to $.94^*(6.76)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level is in accordance with research hypothesis number 4 which states that the 8 Ps of marketing strategy have a direct influence on management innovation.
5. The 8 Ps marketing strategy (EGSTG) has a direct influence on the success of coffee shop operators in Thailand (SCSOT) with a coefficient of influence equal to $.49^*(6.21)$ Statistically significant at the .05 level, according to research hypothesis number 5, which is stated that the 8 Ps marketing strategy has a direct influence on the success of coffee shop operators in Thailand.
6. Innovation Management (INMNG) has a direct influence on the success of coffee shop operators in Thailand (SCSOT) with an influence coefficient equal to $.67^*(3.96)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level is in accordance with research hypothesis number 6, which states that Management innovation has a direct influence on the success of coffee shop operators in Thailand.
7. Innovation Management (INMNG), Entrepreneurial Leadership (ETPLDS), 8Ps Marketing Strategy (EGSTG) can work together to predict the success of coffee shop operators in Thailand (SCSOT) was 89 percent.
8. Entrepreneurial Leadership (ETPLDS), Business Operations Ability (ABLBUS), 8Ps Marketing Strategy (EGSTG) can together predict Innovation Management (INMNG) got .87 percent.

The analysis results can be displayed as follows.

Chi-Square=258.17, df=135, P-value=0.00000, RMSEA=0.048

A success model for coffee shop operators in Thailand Smart Synthesis of success models for coffee shop operators in Thailand in form IOCSS Model (In and Out Coffee Shop Strategy Model) or the full name of this model is “Model of proactive internal and external strategies for the success of Thai coffee shops ” (Insider and Outsider Strategy for Success of Coffee Shop Entrepreneurs in Thailand: In and Out Strategy) found that this model presents strategies for creating Two main strategies have been achieved : (1) Inside Strategy it gives importance to the internal operations of the coffee shop. Entrepreneurs must take the lead in developing internal management systems in three important areas: developing teamwork skills; Development of internal management systems and development of organizational innovation (2) Outside Strategy is an emphasis on the perception (Perception) of customers and the general public who have the coffee shop's products and services. It gives importance to operations. Entrepreneurs must take the lead in developing awareness in three important areas: awareness of the quality of coffee and employees who provide excellent and friendly service. Creating a memorable and outstanding image of the coffee shop Creating conditions for returning to use the service.

Insider and Outsider Strategy for Success of Coffee Shop Entrepreneurs in Thailand: In and Out Coffee Shop Strategy Model, It is a strategy for managing both making The management process within the coffee shop is sufficiently efficient and managing communications with external customers to create a positive perception of the coffee shop. This process will start from Entrepreneurial is the first person who must truly see the importance of such change. Must have Entrepreneurial Mindset because it will require continuous investment. both from finding new innovations used in coffee shops Both management innovation and innovation in

food and beverages. In addition, Must also be the main person in driving employees to move in the same direction. With a clear work policy providing compensation to employees that is reasonable and sufficient to create motivation for work. Entrepreneurial, Staff) must give importance to competitor analysis and market analysis to understand before starting to collaborate on Inside Strategy and Outside Strategy analysis.

Competitor analysis): Currently, a large number of coffee shops are popping up in Thailand. Either they are the market leader or a big brand that has a good reputation and coffee shops that are characteristics of small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) and coffee shops are spread all over the country. Can be easily accessed. Entrepreneurs and service employees (Staff) must jointly analyze and understand first that Competitor coffee shops in the same area In a similar size What does it look like? Including analysis of the products, coffee, food, atmosphere, and service of the coffee shop. Compared to big brands Are there any differences or similarities in the issues? The issues in the analysis are as follows:

Price: This is to check whether competitors are close to each other. Coffee is served in the same way. The price is set the same for each type of product sold. This includes checking product prices with large brand coffee shops. In this regard, such inspection will compare the status of the coffee shop, who they are competing with, and how much difference there is in the prices offered by different coffee shops.

Shop Decoration: This is to check whether competing stores that are nearby are similar. It is also to understand the customer's choice. The characteristics of the shop's decoration are being assessed. Additionally, we are examining what customers think about the decoration of this store. We are identifying the strengths that customers like. This information will be compared with other coffee shops to inform development and create differentiation and prominence.

Location: This is to check whether competing stores provide services in similar areas. The advantages include being more convenient and easier to access, considering the proximity of public transportation that allows for easy and comfortable travel, being centrally located in the community and clearly visible, and having parking available for those who come to use the service.

Appearance: It is to check the image of the competitor. Customers who have used the services in the competing stores share their opinions on the image. This includes aspects such as confidence in the image, customer relations, and trust with customers. These opinions will be compared with those of the coffee shop to see how it stands against competitors.

Product and service quality: It is to check whether the competitors in the same area and large brands who offer to sell the same type of goods and services. This will reveal the quality of products and services, the strength of the competitors, and how the coffee shop compares to its competitors.

CONCLUSION

1. The sample group that collected data by questionnaire was mostly female, numbering 206. People accounted for 51.50 percent. Age between 36 - 45 years, number 156 People accounted for 39.00 percent. Bachelor's degree level: 212 People accounted for 53.00 percent. Business income / month less than 1,000,000 baht, amount 248 People accounted for 62.00 percent.
2. The results of the survey of variables studied in the model found that all variables were at a high level. They are arranged in descending order as follows: The success of coffee shop operators in Thailand (SCSOT) is at a high level. has an average of 4.43, followed by entrepreneurial leadership (ETPLDS) with an average of 4.36, management innovation (INMNG) with an average of 4.34, business ability (ABLBUS) with an average of 4.32, and strategy Marketing 8Ps (EGSTG) has an average of 4.16
3. Results of the study of structural equation modeling on the influence of entrepreneurial leadership variables. Ability to conduct business 8Ps marketing strategies and management innovations that affect the success of coffee shop operators in Thailand, the adjustment process (Adjust Model) is in harmony with the empirical data at an acceptable level. which is considered from the Harmony Index (Fit Index) as follows: $\chi^2 = 258.17$, $df = 135$, p -value = .00000, $\chi^2/df = 1.91$, RMSEA = .048, RMR = .027, SRMR = .037, CFI = .99, GFI = .94, AGFI = .91, CN = 274.68. The estimation was found in the structural equation model as follows: (1) Entrepreneurial leadership (ETPLDS) has a direct influence on the success of coffee shop operators in Thailand (SCSOT) with an influence coefficient equal to .42*(2.71) is statistically significant at the .05 level (2) Entrepreneurial leadership (ETPLDS) has a direct influence. continue Management innovation (INMNG) with an influence coefficient equal to .76*(5.46) with statistical significance at the .05 level (3) Business operations ability (ABLBUS) has a direct influence on Innovation Management (INMNG) with an influence coefficient of .77*(6.78) with statistical significance at the level of .05 (4) 8 Ps Marketing Strategy (EGSTG) has a direct influence on Innovation Management (INMNG) with an influence coefficient of .94*(6.76) with statistical significance at the level of .05 (5) 8 Ps Marketing Strategy (EGSTG) has a direct influence on The success of coffee shop operators in Thailand (SCSOT) with an influence coefficient equal to .49*(6.21) is statistically significant at the .05 level (6). Management innovation (INMNG) has a direct influence on the success of coffee shop operators in Thailand (SCSOT) with an influence coefficient equal to .67*(3.96) is statistically significant at the .05 level.
4. Results of developing a success model for coffee shop operators in Thailand. It has been presented in the form of the IOCSS Model or the full name of this model is "Internal and external proactive strategy model for the success of Thai coffee shops." (Insider and Outsider Strategy for Success of Coffee Shop Entrepreneurs [23] in Thailand: In and Out Strategy) it was found that this model presented two main strategies for creating success: (1) Inside Strategy It gives importance to the internal operations of the coffee shop. Entrepreneurs must take the lead in developing internal management systems in three

important areas: developing teamwork skills [24]; Development of internal management system and development of organizational innovation (2) Outside Strategy is an emphasis on the perception (Perception) of customers and the general public who have the coffee shop's products and services. It is important to focus on operations. Entrepreneurs must take the lead in developing awareness in three important areas: awareness of the quality of coffee and employees [25]; Excellent and friendly service providers creating a memorable and outstanding image of the coffee shop Creating conditions for returning to use the service.

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